

Gastric cancer: Current treatment options and future perspectives - A systematic review

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This is an original research protocol.

1. Background

Gastric cancer is a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide, with high complexity in its treatment due to late diagnosis and the variety of therapeutic needs (Kopecky 2022). This systematic review aims to synthesize the existing literature on current treatment modalities such as surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and targeted therapies. It will also explore novel and emerging approaches, including immunotherapies and personalized treatments, aiming to provide a detailed understanding of future advancements (Baccili Cury Megid 2023). This review will examine the overall survival rate as a key metric for evaluating treatment success and viability in improving patient outcomes. A comprehensive review of available treatments and emerging therapies is essential to inform future research, patient care strategies and policy makers.

This protocol serves as the foundational framework for conducting the systematic review on gastric cancer treatments and future perspectives.

2. Research Questions

2.1 Primary Research Question:

What are the current standard treatment options for gastric cancer, and how are emerging therapies and future research directions expected to improve patient outcomes?

2.2 Secondary Research Questions:

None.

3. Review Team and Contributors

- **[Imane El Amri]:** conceptualization, methodology, data collection, data analysis, validation, investigation

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All team members will contribute to data collection, analysis, and the writing of the review.

4. Type of Review

This is a systematic review no meta-analysis will be conducted, and the review will follow the PRISMA guidelines for reporting systematic reviews (Page 2021). The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) will be employed to assess the risk of bias in the included observational studies.

5. Search Strategy

5.1 Databases:

The following databases will be searched:

- PubMed (MEDLINE): for clinical trials, observational studies, and systematic reviews in the field of cancer treatment.
- Scopus: for a broad range of scientific literature including observational studies on gastric cancer treatments.
- Google Scholar: to capture studies non-indexed in PubMed or Scopus.

A comprehensive search of these databases will cover publications published in recent years, from 2013 to 2024, and will be restricted to studies in English and French languages.

5.2 Other Search Strategies or Resources:

- Backward Citation Tracking: References of identified systematic reviews will be reviewed for relevant articles.
- Forward Citation Tracking: Studies citing the included literature will be evaluated to ensure comprehensive coverage.

5.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies published from 2013 and 2024.
- Studies published in English or French languages.
- Observational studies focused on adults (age >18) with gastric cancer.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Non-English/French studies.
- Studies published before 2013.
- Studies not focused on gastric cancer and its therapy.

- Studies with less than 30 gastric cancer cases

5.4 Search Strings or Queries:

Search strings will focus on keywords related to gastric cancer treatments, including "gastric cancer," "chemotherapy," "immunotherapy," "surgery," "radiotherapy," "targeted therapy".

The following search string is currently undergoing testing on the aforementioned databases: (Gastric OR Stomach) AND (Cancer OR Neoplasm OR Tumor* OR Adenocarcinoma OR Gastrointestinal stromal OR neuroendocrine OR lymphoma*) AND (treatment OR therapy OR antineoplastic OR neoadjuvant OR immunotherapy OR chemotherapy OR molecular targeted therapy)

5.6 Search Strategy Justification:

The selected databases and search strategies ensure broad coverage of indexed literature on gastric cancer treatments in over a decade. PubMed will provide clinical and medical perspectives, while Scopus and Google Scholar will include multidisciplinary sources.

6. Screening and Selection

6.1 Screening Stages:

- Stage 1: Title and abstract screening based on predefined eligibility criteria.
- Stage 2: Full-text screening of shortlisted papers. Reasons for exclusion will be documented.

6.2 Screening Tool(s):

- Rayyan Software will be used for screening and decision-tracking (Ouzzani 2016).

6.3 Screener Instructions:

Three reviewers will independently screen articles. Discrepancies will be resolved by consensus, and if unresolved, a fourth reviewer will be consulted.

7. Data Extraction

7.1 Data Items:

The characteristics of the included studies: :

- study characteristics (first author, publication year, country of the research);
- study methods (study design, patients' inclusion criteria, duration of the study);
- sample characteristics (size, age, gender, ethnicity/race, clinical stage of the gastric cancer, node and metastasis (TNM) classification, presence of metastasis, treatment modality, treatment lines and adverse effects);

- primary and secondary outcomes of the studies, future directions or recommendations provided by the authors.
- quality metrics (e.g., risk of bias)

7.2 Extraction Stages:

Data will be extracted in two stages:

1. Extraction of the principal characteristics of the included studies.
2. Quality and risk of bias data extraction using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS).

7.3 Extraction Tool(s):

Data will be extracted using Microsoft Excel.

7.4 Extractor Instructions:

Data extraction will be conducted independently by two reviewers, with discrepancies resolved by discussion or involving a third reviewer if necessary.

8. Risk of Bias (Quality) Assessment

The NOS will be used to assess the quality of included observational studies (cross-sectional, cohort, and case-control). The NOS evaluates studies based on:

- Selection of participants.
- Comparability of study groups.
- Outcome or exposure ascertainment.

The results of the assessment are presented according to the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) standards. The following are accepted thresholds for converting the NOS to AHRQ standards for cohort and case-control studies (good, fair, and poor quality studies):

- "Good quality: 3 or 4 stars in selection domain AND 1 or 2 stars in compatibility domain AND 2 or 3 stars in outcome/exposure domain"
- "Fair quality: 2 stars in selection domain AND 1 or 2 stars in comparability domain AND 2 or 3 stars in outcome/exposure domain"
- "Poor quality: 0 or 1 star in selection domain OR 0 stars in comparability domain OR 0 or 1 stars in outcome/exposure domain"

The thresholds for cross-sectional studies are the following:

- "Good quality: 4 or 5 stars in selection domain AND 1 or 2 stars in compatibility domain AND 2 or 3 stars in outcome/exposure domain"
- "Fair quality: 2 or 3 stars in selection domain AND 1 or 2 stars in comparability domain AND 2 or 3 stars in outcome/exposure domain"
- "Poor quality: 0 or 1 star in selection domain OR 0 stars in comparability domain OR 0 or 1 stars in outcome/exposure domain"

Two independent reviewers will assess the studies, with conflicts resolved by a third reviewer.

9. Synthesis

9.1 Planned Data Transformations:

No transformations of extracted data are planned.

9.2 Missing or Unclear Data:

Authors of studies with missing or unclear data will be contacted via email for clarification.

9.3 Synthesis Method:

This review will employ a “narrative synthesis” to collate and summarize findings from the included studies. No quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) will be conducted.

9.4 Synthesis Procedure:

The narrative synthesis will involve organizing data by study design and intervention type (e.g., chemotherapy, surgery, immunotherapy). A thematic analysis of emerging treatments will also be conducted.

9.5 Planned Analysis for Confidence in Cumulative Evidence and Meta-Biases:

No formal grading of evidence will be conducted, but bias across studies will be considered during synthesis.

10. Additional Information

- This protocol has received no financial support.

References

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- Kopecky, K., Monton, O., Rosman, L. and Johnston, F., 2022. Palliative interventions for patients with advanced gastric cancer: a systematic review. *Chinese Clinical Oncology*, 11(6), pp.47-47.
- Ouzzani, M., Hammady, H., Fedorowicz, Z. and Elmagarmid, A., 2016. Rayyan—a web and mobile app for systematic reviews. *Systematic reviews*, 5, pp.1-10.
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